

Metallic Compounds of Rubeanic Acid.

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Rubeanic acid may be regarded as a tautomeric compound consisting of an equilibrium mixture of sym.-dithio-oxamide and sym.-di-imido-dithio-oxalic acid. (Wallach and Reinhardt, *Annalen*, 262, 354; Ephraim, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1026). Sodium and lead salts of the acid are mentioned in the literature (*Ber.*, 1880, 13, 528 ; *Annalen*, 38,315). In this paper a systematic investigation of other metallic derivatives has been undertaken.

Rubeanic acid readily gives insoluble precipitates with salts of silver, gold, platinum, zinc, cobalt and nickel. The copper, cobalt and nickel compounds have been prepared and studied, and found to have the formula $\text{MeC}_2\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ (Me=metal). Unlike the lead and sodium salts, the metallic atom in these compounds seems to form the centre of a cyclic co-ordination complex, as indicated in the structural formula given below.

(Me=Cu, Co^{++} or Ni).

The reasons for such an assumption are :—

(i) These compounds are fairly stable and can be heated up to 160° without decomposition, whereas the compounds with sodium, lead (*loc. cit.*) and silver—metals which possess very little residual affinity—are extremely unstable.

(ii) These salts possess characteristic colours differing from those of the usual organic and inorganic salts of cobalt and nickel: copper rubeanate being black, the nickel salt bluish-violet and the cobalt compound reddish-brown.

(iii) The nickel and cobalt salts on digestion with caustic soda solution partially dissolve and the rubeanates are reprecipitated from these solutions on neutralisation of the alkali. The solutions are unaffected by sulphuretted hydrogen or ammonium sulphide.

(iv) With a strongly ammoniacal solution of nickel salts, rubeanic acid gives a brilliant red compound, which readily gives up ammonia and changes to the bluish-violet nickel rubeanate. Also, the latter dissolves in liquor ammonia to a deep orange-red solution from which the original rubeanate is obtained on boiling off the ammonia. The orange-red solution does not, however, contain free nickel or rubeanic acid radical and is, no doubt, due to a combination of nickel rubeanate with further molecules of ammonia. Recalling that nickel tetrammino compounds are stabler than hexammino derivatives, the formula given above, which shows the co-ordination number of nickel to be four, explains the fugitive nature of the red compound in which the nickel atom has possibly a co-ordination number of six.

As might be expected from the structure assigned to these compounds, they are extremely insoluble in water and in all the ordinary organic solvents, 1 part of

nickel in 500,000, 1 part of copper in 1,000,000 and 1 part of cobalt in 150,000 parts of water being immediately precipitated as rubeanates. In fact, nickel and cobalt have been successfully estimated by precipitation as rubeanates; while copper presented some difficulties as regards washing and filtering. With more dilute solutions of copper, nickel and cobalt, rubeanic acid produces characteristic green, blue and yellow colourations respectively; and the sensitiveness of these reactions as tests for the micro-detection of these metals has been determined. The colour-effects can be used to detect 1 part of copper in 30 million, 1 part of nickel in 7 million and 1 part of cobalt in 30 million parts of water.

Carbonato-tetrammino-cobaltic nitrate with rubeanic acid gives tetra-aquo-diammino-tri-rubeanato-dicobalt $[\text{Co}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{Rb})_3]$, where $\text{Rb} = (\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2)''$. It loses the water molecules when heated to $115\text{--}120^\circ$ and is converted into

EXPERIMENTAL.

The rubeanic acid used in these experiments was prepared by passing a rapid current of dry and pure cyanogen gas (free from carbon dioxide) into a freshly-prepared, ice-cold solution of potassium hydrosulphide in absolute alcohol and acidifying the saturated solution with dilute hydrochloric acid (*cf.* Ephraim, *Ber.*, 1889, 23, 2305). The yield was about 70% of the theoretical. (Found: $\text{N} = 23.26$. Calc., $\text{N} = 23.33$ per cent.).

Copper Rubeanate.

The compound was precipitated by adding an alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid to a slight excess of copper sulphate solution, washed by decantation with warm water, filtered on the pump and dehydrated at 105°. Samples prepared in aqueous or ammoniacal solutions, as also in presence of sodium acetate, gave the same composition. (Found: Cu=33·3, 33·2; S=32·85, 32·6; N=14·83, 15·15. $\text{CuC}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{H}_2$ requires Cu=35·0; S=35·2; N=15·4 per cent.).

The results of analysis were always lower than the theoretical values due to adsorption of electrolytes which could not be removed even by prolonged washing.

Properties.—Copper rubeanate when freshly precipitated was a voluminous, slimy, black mass which changed to black, shining scales on drying. It was fairly stable and began to decompose above 160°. When heated, a red liquid distilled over and condensed in the cooler parts of the tube. On heating more strongly the red liquid also decomposed with evolution of sulphur dioxide, ammonia and cyanogen, while a residue of copper oxide was left behind. It was unaffected by ammonia but dissolved in moderately dilute, boiling hydrochloric acid. Boiling caustic alkalis decomposed it into copper sulphide, alkali cyanide and sulphocyanide.

Nickel Rubeanate.

To an aqueous solution of a nickel salt was added the requisite amount of an alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid. There was no precipitation at this stage, but on neutralising the acid liberated during the reaction with the minimum amount of ammonia or sodium acetate, the rubeanate

at once separated out. This was washed by decantation, filtered on the pump and dried at 100° . With a strongly ammoniacal solution of nickel salt, rubeanic acid formed an intensely red compound; but the latter readily changed into the bluish-violet rubeanate even when filtered and desiccated in an atmosphere of ammonia. The bluish-violet rubeanate gave the following results on analysis. (Found: Ni = 33.1; S = 36.6; N = 16.3. $\text{NiC}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires Ni = 33.2; S = 36.2; N = 15.8 per cent.).

Properties.—Nickel rubeanate was precipitated as a slimy mass which changed to a bluish-violet powder on drying. It was fairly stable and decomposed above 160° . It behaved like copper rubeanate on dry distillation.

It was insoluble in water and the common organic solvents; but in pyridine it dissolved to a pink solution the colour being discharged by water. It was also soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid, specially on boiling.

It dissolved partially in 3% ammonia to a bluish-violet solution and more freely in strong ammonia to a deep orange-red solution which contained no $-\text{CNS}'$, $-\text{S}''$ or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4''$ ions, nor did it give any tests for free nickel or free rubeanic acid. From this solution the original bluish-violet rubeanate was reprecipitated on boiling off the ammonia.

It dissolved in caustic alkali to a yellowish-red solution changing to pink on dilution. From these solutions the bluish-violet nickel rubeanate was obtained by neutralisation, on standing overnight or by prolonged boiling. The solutions were unaffected by H_2S or $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}$ and did not contain any $-\text{CNS}'$, $-\text{CN}'$, Ni^{++} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4''$ or $\text{C}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{H}_2''$ ions. These facts proved that caustic alkali did not decompose the rubeanate molecule and that the solvent action was therefore due to some sort of salt-formation like $\text{NiC}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{Na}_2$.

Estimation of Nickel.

The nickel was precipitated as rubeanate in the presence of sodium acetate or ammonia, the precipitate was washed by decantation with hot water, filtered, dried and ignited. The rubeanate decomposed into NiS which changed on further ignition to NiO (*cf.* Cormimboef, *Annali. Chim. Appl.*, 1906, 2, 6). Part of the oxide was reduced to the metallic state by the organic matter. The ignited mass was therefore treated with concentrated nitric acid, the excess of acid evaporated off, the nitrate was heated with a low flame, the temperature being gradually raised to a dull red heat, whereupon the conversion into nickel oxide was complete—the nickel being weighed as NiO. The results obtained are tabulated below.

Ni taken (gms.).	NiO found (gms.).	Ni found (gms.).	Error (gms.).
0.0201	0.0258	0.0203	+0.0003
0.0281	0.0362	0.0285	+0.0004
0.0321	0.0413	0.0325	+0.0004
0.0321	0.0408	0.0321	0.0000
0.0348	0.0441	0.0347	-0.0001
0.0361	0.0460	0.0362	+0.0001
0.0503	0.0635	0.0499	-0.0004
0.0571	0.0732	0.0575	+0.0004
0.0428	0.0545	0.0429	+0.0001
0.0371	0.0475	0.0374	+0.0003
0.0371	0.0476	0.0374	+0.0003
0.0497	0.0634	0.0499	+0.0002
0.0618	0.0791	0.0622	+0.0004
0.0412	0.0528	0.0415	+0.0003

Cobalt Rubeanate.

This compound was prepared, washed and filtered as in the case of nickel. Cobalt rubeanate settled more readily and was easily washed free from soluble matters. It could not be dehydrated even at 120°. (Found : Co=27·2 ; S=30·0 ; N=13·2. $C_2H_2N_2S_2Co, 2H_2O$ requires Co=27·7 ; S=30·1 and N=13·1 per cent.).

Properties.—Cobalt rubeanate was obtained as a reddish-brown, hygroscopic powder that did not lose all its water even at 130°. It began to decompose above 160° and behaved like the copper salt on strong heating, a mixture of cobalt sulphide and cobalt oxide being left behind as a residue. Like the nickel salt, it dissolved undecomposed in hot dilute alkali. It was unaffected by ammonia.

Estimation of Cobalt.

The cobalt was precipitated as rubeanate in the presence of sodium acetate or dilute ammonia ; the precipitate was washed with hot water, filtered, dried and ignited. The ignited mass was then treated with a few drops of concentrated nitric and one drop of concentrated sulphuric acids, converted into and weighed as $CoSO_4$, with the usual precautions. The results obtained are tabulated below.

Co taken (gms.).	$CoSO_4$ found (gms.).	Co found (gms.).	Error (gms.).
0·0208	0·0552	0·0210	+0·0002
0·0208	0·0548	0·0209	+0·0001
0·0208	0·0542	0·0206	—0·0002
0·0208	0·0550	0·0209	+0·0001
0·0416	0·1090	0·0415	—0·0001
0·0416	0·1094	0·0416	0·0000
0·0241	0·0636	0·0242	+0·0001
0·0271	0·0710	0·0270	—0·0001
0·0146	0·0385	0·0147	+0·0001
0·0312	0·0825	0·0314	+0·0002

Presence of ammonium salts and of metals of the fourth (analytical) group did not interfere with the estimation of cobalt and nickel by these methods.

The behaviour of rubeanic acid towards other metals is given below.

Silver nitrate gave a yellow ppt. which passed at once into black silver sulphide.

Mercurous salts gave a white ppt. even from strongly acid solutions. The precipitation was quantitative.

Mercuric salts behaved similarly. The precipitate consisted of an indefinite mixture of rubeanic acid and HgCl' .

Cadmium salts gave a yellowish-white ppt. only in presence of sodium acetate. It was soluble in acids and was decomposed by alkalis into CdS , NaCN and NaSCN . The compound changed slowly in the cold and more rapidly on boiling into CdS .

With zinc a white ppt. was obtained in neutral solution only. It behaved like the cadmium compound towards acids and alkali.

Gold and platinum gave brownish-black precipitates.

Tetra-aquo-di-ammino-tri-rubeanato-dicobalt.

To a solution of 4 g. of carbonato-tetrammino-cobaltic nitrate in 120 c.c. of water made ammoniacal with 40 c.c. of 8% ammonia was added an alcoholic solution of 1 g. of rubeanic acid (about a third of the theoretical amount) with constant stirring. There was an instantaneous precipitation. The precipitate was allowed to settle, washed with very dilute ammonia, filtered on the pump and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. (Found: $\text{Co} = 20.64, 20.46$; $\text{S} = 32.8, 33.1$; $\text{N} = 19.5, 18.95$; Loss on drying

at $115-20^{\circ}=11.9$. $\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{H}_2)_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{NH}_3)_2$ requires
 $\text{Co}=20.4$; $\text{S}=33.2$; $\text{N}=19.3$; $\text{H}_2\text{O}=12.3$ per cent.).

The compound was obtained as a dull brown powder insoluble in water, dilute hydrochloric acid and the usual organic solvents. Boiling alkalis decomposed it with evolution of ammonia. The compound did not contain nitrate or carbonate radicles, and the cobalt was in the cobaltic condition. The substance after being dried at $115-20^{\circ}$ gave, on analysis, $\text{N}=21.2$. $\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{H}_2)_3(\text{NH}_3)_2$ requires $\text{N}=21.7$ per cent.

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